

DUTCH NATIONAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SOCIAL SCIENCE

ODISSEI

Annual Report

2025

Bringing together sensitive data, computing resources, and expertise to drive collaborative social science and economic research across the Netherlands.

1,890
PUBLICATIONS

45
MEMBER
ORGS

10,137
PORTAL
DATASETS

1,500+
EVENT
ATTENDEES

Daniel Oberski

Scientific Director, ODISSEI
Chair, Management Board

A year of maturation and commitment

"ODISSEI has grown into an indispensable national infrastructure – one that not only connects data, but connects people, disciplines, and institutions in service of research that matters."

"ODISSEI has grown into an indispensable national infrastructure — one that not only connects data, but connects people, disciplines, and institutions in service of research that matters."

Modern social science increasingly depends on data survey responses, administrative records, and digital traces that are sensitive, fragmented, and difficult to bring together safely. ODISSEI is the Dutch national infrastructure that solves this problem. We enable data, secure computing power, and methodological expertise to be together in one place, so that researchers across the Netherlands can study the questions that matter. ODISSEI users study a diverse range of topics, from inequality and health to work and democracy, without each having to build the technical scaffolding themselves. In short, we are the connective tissue of Dutch social science, its infrastructure.

2025 was a year in which that infrastructure came of age. Core technical services such as the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer, the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), and the ODISSEI Portal, each reached new levels of capability and accessibility. SANE alone now supports over 30 active research projects. SANE, Data Donation Infrastructure, and FIRMBACKBONE were awarded structural funding from the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, ensuring these investments will continue to deliver for years to come. Alongside this, LISS was able to deliver quick turnover for the Dutch national election study, in addition to its already-impressive portfolio of studies supported.

This trust was echoed by our community. We now count 45 member organisations and 1,890 publications enabled by our facilities. This work will continue to expand as in late 2025 we were awarded €16.8 million to build the world's first population scale MacroScope, harnessing a range of world class facilities that are already in place in the Netherlands and making them a single, interoperable, and scale instrument to support social research. Work on the MacroScope is on track to deliver the most ambitious lens into the complexity of human behaviour yet for Dutch researchers.

Equally important is the human side of our work. The ODISSEI Conference brought together 440 researchers, our Summer School trained a new generation of computational social scientists, and the SoDa team provided hands-on support to researchers navigating ever more complex data. I am proud of what ODISSEI has achieved, and look ahead to a future defined by even greater collaboration, openness, and research impact.

Governance

ODISSEI is the Dutch National Infrastructure that brings together sensitive data, computing resources and expertise to drive collaborative social science and economic research. It now consists of **45 member organisations**, with 31 already committed to membership through 2031.

SUPERVISORY BOARD

Claes de Vreese	DSW — Chair
Viola Angelini	DEB
Hanneke Imbens	Statistics Netherlands
Beate Volker	KNAW / NWO Institutes & E-Infrastructures
Susan Branje	DSW
Maarten van Ham	DSW
Paulette Flore	Public Research Institutes

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Daniel Oberski	Utrecht University — Chair
Tom Emery	EUR — Executive Director
Dorret Boomsma	VU Amsterdam
Jessica Piotrowski	University of Amsterdam
Marcel Das	Centerdata
Ran van den Boom	Statistics Netherlands
Annette Langedijk	SURF
Colette Bos	NLeSC
Anja Smit	DANS
Jacco van Ossenbruggen	VU Amsterdam

COORDINATION TEAM

Tom Emery	Director
Lucas van der Meer	Chief Technical Officer
Kasia Karpinska	Scientific Manager
Theodora Canciu	Project Manager
Evgeniia Krichever	Communications Manager
Angelica Maineri	Data Manager

INTERNATIONAL ADVISORY BOARD

Julia Lane	New York University
Melinda Mills	University of Oxford
Sally Wyatt	Maastricht University
Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch	CESSDA
Amy O'Hara	Georgetown University

Access, security, and infrastructure

Improved data access, secure computing, and technical innovation — expanding dataset availability, improving metadata search and linkage, developing the Secure Supercomputer and SANE environments, and deepening collaborations with CBS and SURF.

In 2025, ODISSEI continued its efforts to remove barriers to accessing sensitive data. The major achievements included expanding services, such as CBS Data Storage (for reusing large data sets created from microdata that require substantial computational effort to produce), and introducing a discount on project start-up costs, thereby improving accessibility for researchers. The Microdata Access Grant, a flagship programme of ODISSEI that covers the costs of a microdata project, was offered twice in 2025, resulting in **12 new projects**. To accommodate increased usage, CBS developed a self-service portal that enhances user control over projects and microdata use.

In the ODISSEI Portal, improvements strengthened metadata quality, findability, and reuse, and these efforts further fuelled the development of a broad **ODISSEI Knowledge Graph**, which aims to connect literature, tools, datasets, variables, projects, organisations, and authors. The first version of the Knowledge Graph is available as a proof of concept. Also, the **Data Access Broker (DAB)**, a SURF service that standardises data access conditions across data providers in the SSH ecosystem and automatically pre-processes access requests, has reached the proof of concept stage, paving the way for the service's full implementation.

Progress in secure compute infrastructure was marked by ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer's (OSSC) innovations, including the **Trusted Upload and Linkage Procedure (TULP) pilot**, which allows researchers to upload very large datasets to the OSSC, with additional safeguards for sharing sensitive data with CBS. The **App Dashboard was finalised**, offering researchers a graphical user interface, thereby further lowering the technical barriers to using secure environments. In parallel, the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE) matured into a scalable, widely accessible infrastructure with **over 32 active research projects** in 2025, while Firmbackbone strengthened its data integration and user base. Both SANE and Firmbackbone have been awarded structural funding from the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science.

ACTUAL EXPENDITURE 2025	€1,462,000
Data Facility Workstream	
Hardware & software capabilities	€655,077
Metadata interoperability & enrichment (KG, DAB)	€529,000
Innovative approaches to microdata	€144,000
Microdata Access grants & discounts	€90,000
Firmbackbone — company data access	€43,923

Data collections for the long run

Sustaining and developing data collections enabling Dutch researchers to conduct longitudinal, comparative, and population-level social science research — in line with FAIR principles and ethical data practices.

2025 was a year of notable activity for the Observatory across data collection, infrastructure, and international collaboration. The ODISSEI LISS panel grant received a **record number of applications**, doubling the number of awarded projects to fifteen, and enabling more researchers to collect data free of charge. The representativeness of the LISS panel was strengthened through a revised sampling strategy developed with Statistics Netherlands, which improved the coverage of **hard-to-reach population groups**. ODISSEI has also established a FAIR Implementation Profile for the LISS Data Archive to improve data findability and reusability. Sensitive LISS data became accessible through the Secure Analysis Environment (SANE), with a research project successfully combining location-enriched LISS data with high-resolution geospatial data — demonstrating in practice the cross-facility data linkage that ODISSEI's infrastructure is designed to enable.

In 2025, ODISSEI made concrete progress in meeting growing researcher demand for data beyond traditional surveys. The **PANL participant recruitment platform** completed testing and moved toward full production following secured structural funding. Port software enabled structured data collection from major digital platforms, including Instagram, TikTok, Google, and Facebook. At the same time, the International Institute for Social History (IISH) worked on the transcription of **personal record cards covering 1939–1994** via OCR, contributing standardisation expertise and SANE serving as the disclosure infrastructure.

In 2025, ODISSEI supported major international survey data collections: **SHARE Wave 10** was completed and released with wave 11 set to be completed in 2026; data from **ESS Round 12** was collected for the first time using a mixed-mode approach and achieving a response rate of over 50%; the European Values Study prepared for data collection in 2026; and ODISSEI provided financing for the **Dutch Parliamentary Election Study** which fielded ahead of the General Election in November. ODISSEI also financed the collection of the ISSP Module on Work Orientations and paid the membership for the Netherlands in the Luxembourg Income Study which harmonizes income and wealth data from 53 countries.

ACTUAL EXPENDITURE 2025

€1,586,725

Observatory Workstream

SHARE Wave 10	€474,707
ESS Round 12	€367,270
Dutch Parliamentary Election Study	€147,610
LISS panel grant & service	€485,000
Luxembourg Income Study	€30,000
ISSP	€30,380
Genealogical Linkage	€51,758

Innovation at the frontier

Strengthening ODISSEI's capacity for data-intensive social science by advancing secure distributed processing, data donation, population-scale network analysis (PlaNet-NL), and mass online experimentation — with a focus on usability, scalability, and integration.

Within secure distributed processing, progress was centred on the continued development of the **Digital Data Donation Infrastructure and Port**. Key achievements included prioritising the next development phase, introducing parameters to inform panel providers about participant status, and successfully completing a pilot study with Motivaction. Work also advanced on iFrame integration, with proposals refined alongside panel stakeholders. In parallel, the restructuring of the Feldspar repository improved system stability, while reusable Python modules and platform-specific scripts were consolidated, enabling more efficient and privacy-preserving data collection workflows.

The data donation infrastructure moved from project-specific implementations toward a **shared, reusable framework**. Standard scripts, documented workflows, and a clearer organisational model now mean that new research teams can build on existing work rather than starting from scratch. Within **PlaNet-NL**, progress focused on scaling population-wide network analysis and embedding the infrastructure more firmly within ODISSEI — including strengthening collaboration with CBS Microdata Services, advancing methods for temporal and relational analysis, and improving interoperability of large-scale administrative network data.

Work on mass online experiments produced more uneven results. A first **oTree-based use case** was successfully developed and is ready for piloting, while earlier challenges clarified the limitations of existing tools. As a result, the workstream has moved toward more robust and scalable experimental designs, often combining survey, behavioural, and administrative data. Across all components, the key achievement was increasing integration and usability, positioning the Laboratory as a foundation for scalable, privacy-aware, and computationally advanced social science research.

ACTUAL EXPENDITURE 2025	€384,000
Laboratory Workstream	
Port operations & D3I infrastructure	€186,000
Mass online experiments feasibility	€110,000
Population networks — PlaNet-NL	€88,000

Community, training, support

The operational centre of ODISSEI — coordinating daily operations, managing grants, and facilitating cross-institutional engagement so that researchers can focus on their work while strategic priorities and operational delivery remain aligned.

In 2025, the **ODISSEI Conference** brought together 440 researchers, becoming the central part of the community engagement for ODISSEI. The event provided a platform for methodological exchange, interdisciplinary collaboration, and knowledge sharing. Beyond the conference, thematic events, grant support sessions, and invited presentations at universities and research institutions extended ODISSEI's reach. A regular newsletter, podcast, and growing digital community with **over 3,100 followers** on LinkedIn and Bluesky ensure that the community remains informed of developments, funding opportunities, and new resources throughout the year.

Supporting researchers in analysing complex, linked and often sensitive data remains a core focus. The **SoDa team** provides hands-on guidance for methodological and technical challenges. The **SoDa Fellowship programme** ran two application rounds, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and enabling researchers to explore advanced analytical approaches.

Training and capacity building remain central to ODISSEI's activities. The **ODISSEI-SICSS Summer School** trained 24 early-career researchers in infrastructure use and advanced analytical methods. Two SoDa workshops, averaging 25 participants, introduced applications of Large Language Models, secure analysis in SANE, and community-developed tools. Tutorials and training materials were published online, extending their reach beyond individual events and contributing to a growing network of researchers skilled in working with complex data.

ACTUAL EXPENDITURE 2025	€1,646,000
Hub Workstream	
Research support & fellowships	€869,000
Project management & communications	€622,000
Educational activities	€155,000

Research Spotlight

Selected publications enabled by ODISSEI's data infrastructure in 2025, demonstrating the breadth and policy relevance of research conducted using ODISSEI facilities.

LABOUR ECONOMICS · REGISTER DATA

Wage Premium or Wage Penalty? Gendered Long-term Wage Development of Family Caregivers

Labour Economics · Register Data

Raiber, K., Möhring, K., Visser, M., & Verbakel, E. (2026). Work, Employment and Society, 40(1), 3–25.

FUTURE OF WORK · LISS PANEL

Why are employees most susceptible to automation least likely to retrain?

Future of Work · LISS Panel

Jansen, G., Janssen, S., Levels, M., & Fregin, M.-C. (2025). Economic and Industrial Democracy, 0(0).

From Our Researchers

“

The ODISSEI SICSS Summer School provided me with very valuable hands-on experience applying computational methods to Dutch company datasets. Our work culminated in a plenary presentation at the annual ODISSEI conference, offering a great platform to share our findings with a wide professional audience. This experience boosted my skills and expanded my professional network.

Koen Steenks

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam · SICSS Summer School participant

“

Joining the SoDa team as a fellow has greatly shaped how I approach my research. Through meetings with fellow researchers and the broader SoDa team, I gained insights into new data science approaches that now enable me to enhance my own research line by combining multiple levels of analysis and using diverse data sources. Becoming a SoDa fellow has been a great learning experience, and it has exceeded my expectations.

Maïke Weipler

Utrecht University · SoDa Fellow

Financial Report 2025

DATA FACILITY
€1,462,000

 Secure infrastructure,
metadata, access grants

OBSERVATORY
€1,586,725

 Survey data collections, LISS
panel, PaNL

LABORATORY
€384,000

 Port, PlaNet-NL, online
experiments

HUB
€1,646,000

 Operations, training,
community engagement

TOTAL 2025
€5,078,725

All workstreams combined

LINE ITEM	AMOUNT
Data Facility	€1,462,000
Hardware & software capabilities	€655,077
Metadata interoperability & enrichment (KG, DAB)	€529,000
Innovative approaches to microdata	€144,000
Microdata Access grants & discounts	€90,000
Firmbackbone — company data access	€43,923
Observatory	€1,586,725
SHARE Wave 10	€474,707
ESS Round 12	€367,270
Dutch Parliamentary Election Study	€147,610
LISS panel grant & service	€485,000
Luxembourg Income Study	€30,000
ISSP	€30,380
Genealogical Linkage	€51,758
Laboratory	€384,000
Port operations & D3I infrastructure	€186,000
Mass online experiments feasibility	€110,000
Population networks — PlaNet-NL	€88,000
Hub	€1,646,000
Research support & fellowships	€869,000
Educational activities	€155,000
Project management & communications	€622,000
Total Actual Expenditure 2025	€5,078,725

Key Performance Indicators

DATA & ACCESS

- Receive project proposals from 80% of ODISSEI member organisations, currently 63%
- Provide access to 50% of ODISSEI member organisations by 2030, currently 38%
- 50 active SANE projects by 2026, currently 32
- 30 active OSSC projects by 2029, currently 16
- 500 unique visitors to the Portal per month by 2026, currently 414

COMMUNITY & TRAINING

- 500 ODISSEI Conference attendees, 440 in 2025
- 75% of Faculties using the educational programme, currently 42%
- 250 unique attendees at training events per year, 114 in 2025
- 5,000+ LinkedIn & Bluesky followers, currently 3,100
- 100 SoDa projects completed before end of 2029, currently 45

RESEARCH OUTPUT

- 3,000 publications in registry by 2029, currently 1,890
- 1,000 citations per year for ODISSEI papers by 2030, currently 216
- 20 publications describing ODISSEI by 2030, currently 9
- Averaging response rates of 50%+ in surveys by 2030, currently 37%
- 500,000 LISS panel minutes free to researchers per year by 2030, currently 300,000
-

odissei-data.nl

© 2025 ODISSEI — DUTCH NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SOCIAL SCIENCE